

VIEWS ON ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN THE EDUCATION OF ENLIGHTENED PEOPLE

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Abstract: In this article, representatives of Jadid, as intellectual and selfless children of their people, are increasingly occupying a central place in social life. and impact on nature, positive and negative consequences of this impact, technical development and its prospects, rational use of natural resources, etc.

Key words: national heritage, tradition, love, science, civilizations, integration, historical necessity, international ecological political relations, ecological thinking, ecological outlook, social existence, social consciousness, science and technology, ecological culture, ecological education, environmental education.

INTRODUCTION

The ecological reforms being implemented in the new stage of development of Uzbekistan require the implementation of consistent and continuous changes in the field of education. He demands creative changes in the field of personnel training in line with global standards. Our creative people have been studying the national heritage of our ancestors and the age-old values, traditions, and customs of our people and using them for the development of our country. Scientific-theoretical studies are being carried out in world science on the ethnoecology of peoples, the harmony of ethno-aesthetic relations with natural phenomena and everyday lifestyle, and the study of the reflection of ecological consciousness and culture in the culture of peoples. "The most important issue is that we must seriously focus on increasing the ecological culture of the population. ...This can be achieved by cultivating love for mother nature in the hearts of the young generation, a sense of belonging to her." Therefore, in addition to improving the activities of education and promotion of environmental culture in our republic, it is an objective necessity to develop and develop the scientific and theoretical foundations of the tendencies to restore and develop the values of ecological culture of the Uzbek people. . Ecological culture, first of all, consists in preserving the environment without harming it,

with a deep understanding of the laws of nature. The development of ecological culture is related to the provision of information to the population about the development of the ecological consciousness of the people, and the strengthening of propaganda. Therefore, ecological education is at the heart of ecological culture. Therefore, in the ideas and actions of the moderns on the reform of education, there are issues of raising the social consciousness of the nation, especially the formation of the ecological worldview. Through this, it is known from the sources that the Jadids made a special effort to preserve the ecological condition of the country, the natural development of the environment, the purity of the soil, water and air.

Jadidism movement and Jadid thinkers considered it a mass public movement that focused its efforts on solving problems related to environmental protection, improvement of the ecological situation, and protection of people's health. As the material and spiritual culture of the people develops, its history also deepens. Living conditions, rituals and traditions of each nation were formed during the historical development of this nation.

Along with the articles and researches of the Jadids in the spirit of the organization of a new national statehood, school-education and study-teaching, a new attitude to the historical and cultural-spiritual heritage, the motherland inherited by the ancestors of the people of Turkestan, its priceless scientific-journalistic, pedagogical, artistic works were also created, expressing opinions on the preservation of water and soil, clean air, and natural resources. The works of this direction naturally show how the Enlightenment movement emerged as a great and important force in the process of national awakening that began at the beginning of the last century.

To the policy of "Russification", which is occupying an increasingly central place in social life, as the intellectual and selfless children of its people, as well as to the impact of technical progress, new production methods and means on society and nature, which have not been tried before for the Turkestan region. They did not look indifferently at the topical issues raised on the agenda of the time, such as the secret, the positive and negative consequences of this influence, technical development and its prospects, rational use of natural resources. For example, the "Oyina" magazine published by the famous Uzbek scientist and publisher, writer and playwright Mahmudhoja Behbudi helps to awaken the consciousness of our people, introduce them to their identity, glorify national values, and promote the achievements of modern science. played a major role in revitalizing social thought. Although the magazine has been active for less than 3 years, its

pages cover the issues of the nation and its rights, historical development, language and literature, the changes taking place in the world and the related issues. along with a lot of information about the works, articles were also published in the spirit of a reasonable attitude to mother nature. In our opinion, it is necessary to accept Behbudi's words that "only when the nation understands itself, it can intervene in social and political issues equally with others" in a broad sense. So, although the concept of ecological culture did not exist during the modernist movement, the issues of forming a rational attitude to nature were raised in their ideas.

Another famous representative of Jadidism, Saidnosir Mirjalil son, deeply felt that water is a matter of life and death for the people of Turkestan, and after the February revolution of 1917, he drew public attention to this urgent issue, and in his article "Water issue in Turkestan" q, so there is no life in Turkestan," he wrote.

The ideas of Abdurauf Fitrat, a well-known modern enlightener, have given a special attention to ecological issues in the Turkestan region, environmental protection, rational treatment of nature, efficient use of natural resources. He also promoted the reformation of society, modernization of education, introduction of a new approach, and reasonable attitude to the environment and nature. In his works such as "Discussion" and "Story of an Indian Tourist", he pays special attention to the issue of cleanliness in the villages and cities of Turkestan and Bukhara Emirate. In his moral work "Leadership Salvation", he covers his views on cleanliness and environmental education more widely. The great Allama Fitrat considers the importance of cleanliness especially in the education of children, for their maturity and health. Fitrat thinks that femininity and cleanliness are of great importance in the upbringing of children. Refinement and cleanliness are as important to older people as they are ten times more important to younger people. He emphasizes that children should strictly follow the rules of personal hygiene. Alloma touched upon the importance of fresh air in the education of a child, air is more important for a person than food. It is possible to stay five or six hours without food, but not even a minute without air. Therefore, it is necessary to take the children to the fresh air, to the ponds.

In his philosophical views, Abdurauf Fitrat calls children to love and protect the environment. In his textbooks and manuals, he conveyed many of his philosophical thoughts about nature to students in modern schools.

Fitrat's short story "The Indian Tourist" is told in the language of an Indian Muslim tourist who came to Bukhara. In fact, the Indian tourist is the author himself. In the work, the culture, medicine, industry, and even the use of underground resources for the benefit of the people, the spiritual and material wealth of the country are discussed. In the language of an Indian tourist, Fitrat speaks about cleanliness and health care in Bukhara and emphasizes the need to open a higher medical school - Dorush-shifa in the city. In the play, Fitrat, in the image of a Russian doctor, expresses his opinion that his compatriots should be seen as cultured, clean and educated people like in European countries.

In Fitrat's work "The Story of an Indian Tourist", he reveals issues related to nature protection that should be solved at the global level, not within the framework of Movaraunnahr. He expresses the following opinion about the effective use of lands belonging to the Bukhara Emirate: "If these lands of Shahrisabz were in the hands of the Japanese people, they would plant dar and collect dar."

In addition, in scientific treatises of the scholar, he complains about keeping the air of the streets of Bukhara clean and expresses the following points: transferred to us through . First of all, it gets into our food, especially fruits, so they should be washed and eaten. Fourthly, as soon as we breathe, it enters us and settles in some of our internal organs. The solution to this is to keep the city streets clean and the air clean. When you see the wide and neat streets in Farang and Russia, you are amazed, none of them are for eye make-up, but their governments have appointed the right and necessary law for this. Against happiness, the dirtiness of our streets arouses such hatred in us that we are powerless to describe it." However, the cleanliness and tidiness of cities is important for the life of every nation.

Fitrat's broad worldview, mourning for his country, is a proof of his deep understanding of his people and country. We can see that such thoughts depend on artificial irrigation in the East, and it is the basis of ecological education, the support of culture. It is one of the urgent tasks to read the teachings of Fitrat, who created ecological education, thereby enriching our knowledge, to assimilate his views on education, especially on ecological education, as much as possible, and to pass them on to future generations.

Today, we are concerned about the protection of nature, we emphasize the need for efficient and economical use of underground resources, and we sign a number of decisions on environmental protection. Fitrat, in his work "The Story of an Indian Tourist", raised the urgent idea of nature conservation as an

intellectual of the society at that time. In the work, it is thought that "these resources, that is, the underground resources of Movaraunnahr, should be used cleanly and neatly with the help of factories and machines."

The peoples of Central Asia, including the Uzbek people, adhere to the culture of thrift under any circumstances. This applies to all labor-intensive products and everyday life. Among the people, this culture is called "uvol" for short. Surfing and excessive use of natural resources, such as water, soil, and plants, are also harmful. Actions contrary to morals, i.e. a person's excessive eating and drinking, careless use of natural resources in order to gain great wealth, spreading weeds - all these are considered evil. That's why Abdurauf Fitrat called everyone to be aware and wrote: "A nation whose representatives are infected with the disease of waste, there is no doubt that it will perish. If you look at the history of the world, one of the reasons for the destruction of the peoples of the world is this extravagance. This concept, which is less and less used nowadays, applies equally to all layers of people, regardless of who they are. Not spending too much, not overdoing it, being thrifty is not a sign of greed, as some people think. Thrift is a sign of a high level of spiritual culture.

Polluting water, especially spitting on it, is considered a great sin among the Uzbek people. Just like every habit has its root cause, this habit has its reasons. Today, when drinking water is one of the biggest problems, we can achieve certain achievements if we restore our ancient traditions, experiences, and culture of communication with nature.

In his works, we can see Fitrat's thoughts on keeping well water clean, water and soil clean from germs, and maintaining people's health by keeping city streets clean. Alloma's scientific treatises contain the following points. "Ditches in the city, especially in our city, pass under the shacks, wells and ponds are open, the water of hands is not controlled, and the places are definitely the cradle of the blood of various microbes.

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